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Incredulity Toward Success: Pop-Culture in Douglas Coupland's *Generation X*

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Abstract:

The present research paper deals with the postmodernist, pop-cultural analysis of Douglas Coupland's novel *Generation X* which portrays young adult's disillusionment with dominant cultural narratives of success and consumerism. It foregrounds short narratives, jokes, pop-cultural references, and consumer slogans to illustrate meaningless lives of postmodern society which is unable to seek stable identity. The main characters – Andy, Claire, and Dag – reject the corporate American Dream, choosing low-wage jobs and storytelling as acts of resistance to participate in capitalist productivity. They feel trapped in a market system that turns youth culture into branded lifestyle choices ultimately turning them into commodified products.

The paper is divided into three sections: the first section deals with theoretical formulations where the views of Jean-Francois Lyotard on pop-culture and its influences in postmodern society are discussed briefly; the second section analyses the novel from the pop-cultural perspectives; and, the third section concludes the paper with research findings.

Keywords: pop-culture, postmodernism, disillusionment, commodity, meaninglessness, meta-narratives, *Generation X*.

Section I

Postmodernism is a diverse cultural phenomenon that covers wide range of critical thinking and extended to varied fields including science, technology, economics, sociology, and media. Many intellectuals try to capture the postmodern sensibility foregrounding different theoretical aspects such as hybridity, pop-culture, hyperreality, intertextuality, etc. Jean-Francois Lyotard is one of these popular thinkers whose understanding of pop culture emerges from his larger critique of postmodernism, where cultural production reflects the fragmentation of knowledge and the decline of totalizing worldviews. In his work *The Postmodern Condition*, he argues that the contemporary moment is defined by an “incredulity toward metanarratives,” a shift that directly impacts cultural forms (Lyotard, xxiv). Pop culture, rather than aspiring to universal truths, becomes an arena of plurality, where diverse and often contradictory micro-narratives coexist. He suggests that meaning is no longer anchored in authoritative sources but generated through fluid language games in which individuals and groups negotiate identity and value in local contexts. As a result, popular media cultivates a culture of hybridity, play, and surface experimentation, emphasizing style over depth and remix over originality. Furthermore, Lyotard contends that in advanced capitalist societies, knowledge – and by extension culture – is produced “in order to be sold and consumed” (4). Pop culture exemplifies this commodification as it transforms art, communication, and even identity into exchangeable commercial goods governed by market demand. In his discussion of postmodern aesthetics, Lyotard argues that contemporary art no longer seeks to represent reality but “to invent allusions to the conceivable which cannot be presented” highlighting pop culture’s reliance on simulation, irony, and spectacle (81). Thus, Lyotard positions pop culture not merely as entertainment but as a primary site where the dynamics of postmodernism – commodification, fragmentation, and the dissolution of stable meaning – are most visibly enacted.

Section II

Douglas Coupland's novel *Generation X* (1991) is full of pop cultural references and responses of the postmodern society to its dominance. The characters of the novel represent postmodern youths, who do not belong to any nation or to any social class but, on the contrary, they are the citizens of glob facing similar problems and similarly addicted to consumer commodities. The shopping mall is the key product of pop culture, which generates the spirit of consumerism in the postmodern society. The novel focuses on the lives of characters, who are deeply affected by the shopping malls as it becomes an inseparable part of their lives. The argument can be proved in the light of the investigations of Bill Bryson in his book *Made in America* in which he comments that in the early 1990s, "Americans were spending an average of twelve hours a month in shopping malls – more time than they devoted to almost any activity other than sleeping, eating, working, and watching television" (258). The characters in the novel are fascinated with the images of these malls in such a way that even they arrange their food in the shape that will represent the name of mall from which it was purchased. It can be observed in the novel when one of Monroe daughters, Arleen, arranged the food "on a platter in a shape reminiscent of the local shopping mall logo, the Crestwood Mall letter C" that she has prepared for Buck, an astronaut landed on the Texlahoma planet due to space poisoning (Coupland, 42). Coupland not only depicts the fascination of people for shopping mall, but he has also criticised the very idea of shopping mall. In the chapter 'Shopping is not Creating' he reveals that though the planet Texlahoma is served with "running shoes, brass knickknacks, and whimsical greeting cards for unfold millennia," by shopping malls from the earth, it cannot change anything as it permanently remains in the year 1974 (*ibid*). The permanency of the year highlights moral death of the postmodern society which is busy with the shopping carts without realising exact situation of their lives.

People are so much fascinated with the idea of shopping malls that they have created shopping malls at their own houses. This fascination of shopping malls is experienced by Dag in his trip to Nevada where he finds a new development of the houses which are constructed like the blocks three feet away from the highway: "kitchens became the Food Fair; living rooms the Fun Center; the bathroom the Water Park" (71). Dag finds the houses converted into shopping malls.

The frequent reference to television is another pop cultural item in the novel that helps to explore the spirit of the time. Since the explosion of media, television has played central role in shaping the perspectives of postmodern society. It is one of the popular and affordable means that becomes easily available to common people. It has the great impact over the lives of characters of *Generation X*. Andy identifies the weather in Palm Springs just like TV. Dag seeks the help of television to highlight the condition of human being, who is caught in the materialism of the world; whose only aim is to make money and have a fun. He describes this attitude of people just like "animal happiness of people on TV" (30). The only mode Andy and Dag finds to express their thoughts is a television. Their constant references of television prove that their knowledge of environment and society is based on the television.

The television serials are so popular among the members of generation X that they identify others with the television characters. Andy gives a name to Catherine as Elvissa after looking a large "anatomically disproportion head" of a woman on television game show (88). Television is the source of realising the pains of others. Elvissa realises the exploitations of Curtis through her imagination of the television match. She says, "his exploits, most of them about as interesting to me as watching ice hockey on TV" (101-102). Her reliance on television to realise the exploitation of Curtis indicates the influences of it over her life. Television is used to indicate person's ambition: "Tyler is like that old character from TV,

Danny Partridge, who didn't want to work as a grocery store box boy but instead wanted to start out owning the whole store" (106). Further, with the reference from television, he describes his employer's act as "like watching a Bob Hope TV special but with home viewer participation" (111). The addiction to television is aptly expressed in Coupland's neologism 'TELE-PARABLIZING' which he defines as: Morals used in everyday life that derive from TV sitcom plots: "*That's just like the episode where Jan lost her glasses!*" (120). Coupland recognises television as a source that provides necessary morals for everyday life and so his characters wouldn't think a life without television. It is a good solution they find in the absence of other meaningful activities. So it is not possible for them to lead a life without it which can be seen in the novel when Tyler asks Andy: "what do you do down there, anyway? You don't have a TV" (149). Thus, quotes, scenes, crucial events and news from the television are skilfully selected to gather information to express something by comparing with others or by simply applying it to them. Television is the only agent in the process of remembering historical event. Andy remembers Vietnam War only because it is televised recollection. Television helps to form actively his memory about the past. In this regard G. P. Lainsbury rightly claims that "television becomes the medium in which members of Gen X see their situation reflected most clearly, complete with regular breaks for consumerist fantasy or attendance to the needs of the body" (236).

The cloths also reveal the pop cultural influences over the characters in the novel. Dag wears the dress which resembles "the lapsed half of a Mormon pamphleting duo with a white shirt, askew tie, armpits hinged with sweat, 48-hour stubble, gray slacks ("not pants, *slacks*")" (Coupland, 5). Rather Claire's dress is much more illustrative of the influences of this pop culture:

Claire is dressed today in bubble gum capri pants, sleeveless blouse, scarf, and sunglasses: starlet manqué. She likes retro looks, and she also once told us that if she has kids, "I'm going to give them utterly retro names like Madge or Verna or Ralph. Names like people have in diners." (15)

Claire's fondness of retro looks is her desire to express herself with the help of fashion. It is her quest for identity which she is trying to establish through fashion. Her "consumption of cloths is," what Sarup calls, a "way of gaining identity" (105).

Another significant pop cultural item is a food which is affected by various trends in the culture. Its results can be seen in "more people eating away from the home; the use of dietary and herbal supplements; foods for specific groups (e.g., dieters, women, athletes, older adults); the use of convenience and functional foods" (Rodriguez, Web). The use of restaurant food or packed food results in the less use of natural food. The postmodern society is habited to the fast food because it is so easy to buy and prepare. Andy and Dag hate this fast food. Dag says that "you are what you eat" (Coupland, 18). Andy hates fast food because he supposes it is the main reason behind his father's heart attack. So, he has also changed his habit of eating.

The novel also presents the instances that indicate the impacts of pop culture on the global scale which is resulted from the mishmash of all cultures. The world of Texlahoma that is depicted in the novel is the perfect example of how pop culture dominates the world:

It's a sad Everyplace, where citizens are always getting fired from their jobs at 7-Eleven and where the kids do drugs and practice the latest dance crazes at the local lake, where they also fantasize about being adult and pulling welfare-check scams as they inspect each other's skin for chemical burns from the lake

water. Texlahomans shoplift cheap imitation perfumes from dime stores and shoot each other over Thanksgiving dinners every year. And about the only good thing that happens there is the cultivation of cold, unglamorous wheat in which Texlahomans a justifiable pride; by law, all citizens must put bumper stickers on their cars saying: NO FARMERS: NO FOOD. (39)

The planet Texlahoma represents a place on the earth which is saturated with pop culture turning it into a dystopian-like society where there is no guarantee of job and structured social pattern that can ensure the future of people living there. The reference to ‘Everyplace’ paints the picture of hybrid culture resulted out of collage of mainstream cultural anxieties, further creating the fear of losing the job any time and projecting pop-cultural symbol of low wages and frustrations of young generation. The heavy influences of pop culture over world are aptly expressed in Edward’s story:

A shimmering, endless New York shaped of lipsticks, artillery shell, wedding cakes, and folded shirt cardboards; a city built of iron, papier-mache and playing cards; an ugly/lovely world surfaced with carbon and icicles and bougainvillea vines. Its boulevards were patternless, helter-skelter, and cuckoo. Everywhere there were booby traps of mousetraps, triffids, and black holes . . . around any corner there might lurk a clown-tossed marsmallow cream pie, a Brigada Rasa kneecapping, or a kiss from the lovely film star Sophia Loren. (50-51)

Edward, who has locked himself in his private world of words for almost ten years, sees everywhere the images of another world different than his private world. But when he encountered with the real world, he finds that it is saturated with pop culture.

Coupland also distinguishes between the attitudes of members of Generation X and Baby Boomers towards consumerism. The generation of Andy, Dag and Claire is conscious about the exploitation of marketing, whereas the elder generation is greatly involved in it. Their aim is only to purchase whatever they want to have a fun of life. Andy clearly points out that: "Our parents' generation seems neither able nor interested in understanding how marketers exploit them. They take shopping at face value" (68). The marketers have understood that the postmodern era is an era of consumerism where each aspect can be made into commodity. Their realisation of consumer's taste enables them to exploit the consumer. Though Andy, Dag and Claire are aware of the market strategies, they fail to live a desired life in desert. Their mentality is shaped by the luxurious environment to which they belong. Though they choose to live into the desert, they are not free from their materialistic attitude. It is exemplified when Claire demands a perfect apartment. She has hand-refinished, stained and sprinkled hardwood flooring of her apartment. She has decorated the house with the artefacts – racks of antlers and Adirondack chairs. The neologism in the same page further points out that luxuriousness of the postmodern society is nothing but their addiction to the pop cultural aspects:

ARCHITECTURAL INDIGESTION: The almost obsessive need to live in a 'cool' architectural environment. Frequently related objects of fetish include framed black-and-white art photography (Diane Arbus a favourite); simplistic pine furniture; matte black high-tech items such as TVs, stereos, and telephones; low-wattage ambient lighting; a lamp, chair, or table that alludes to the 1950s; cut flowers with complex names. (75)

Coupland's neologism reveals the postmodern attitude of the society, which supposes that their architectural environment can only provide the desired life for them. Each item included in the architectural designing is an aspect of pop culture.

Andy's description of his younger brother Tyler and his friend's is another example of the addiction of the pop cultural items:

The way Global Teens, or Tyler's friends, at least, live their lives so together with each other: shopping, traveling, squabbling, thinking, and breathing . . . no drugs, no irony, and only moderate booze, popcorn, cocoa, and videos on Friday nights. And elaborate wardrobes . . . None of their folks can complain. They're perky. They embrace and believe the pseudo-globalism and ersatz racial harmony of ad campaigns engineered by the makers of soft drinks and computer-inventoried sweaters. Many want to work for IBM when their lives end at the age of twenty-five. (105-106)

However, Coupland has depicted his generation's awareness about the era of consumerism, where everything can be consumed. The characters in the novel are aware that they are becoming the victims of consumerism and try to reject it by moving far away from it. In the chapter 'Shopping is not Creating' Coupland is more suggestive of how the society is committing a mistake by supposing shopping as creating. Coupland's neologism also suggests this rejection of pop culture's dominance in which he writes:

LESSNESS: A philosophy whereby one reconciles oneself with diminishing expectations of material wealth: "*I've given up wanting to make a killing or be a bigshot. I just want to find happiness and maybe open up a little roadside cafe in Idaho*" (54).

The characters in the novel believe that their purchased experiences could not help them to overcome their situation. So they moved to the desert, a place of 'Emallgration,' a neologism which Coupland defines as "migration toward lower-tech, lower-information environments containing a lessened emphasis on consumerism" (173).

Section III

Douglas Coupland's *Generation X: Tales for an Accelerated Culture* is a narrative of resistance against the capitalist and progress-driven ideologies of late twentieth-century America. The characters in the novel reject socially sanctioned narratives of success – corporate employment, suburban family life, consumerism – to create their own micro-narratives in the desert, thereby enacting Lyotard's view that individuals must invent alternative modes of meaning rather than rely on pre-given truths. Further, it puts forth fragmentation, irony, and the proliferation of new cultural forms that challenge hegemonic capitalist narratives. All the main characters are addicted to commodities and think that they cannot live without these commodities; but, it seems that they have been commodified by the capitalist consumer culture. Their addiction to shopping malls for all the necessities of lives points out their systematic commodification in absence of metanarratives. Furthermore, media and television shape their ideological notions which show their incredulity towards successful philosophical foundations that can provide stability to meaningless lives.

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